

INTERACTION OF CYANIDIN WITH A HYDROXYLATED SURFACE (KAOLIN), MODELING THE EFFECT OF pH

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Abstracts

The development of interest in anthocyanins in recent years is associated with an increase in the range of applications of these natural glycosides, contained in plants and berries, the color changes from red to blue with increasing pH. In addition to coloring properties (clay, fabric, hair), the use of anthocyanins – components of red and blue berries (including blueberries) – helps to reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease, Parkinson's disease and more.

Most practical studies concern the interaction of anthocyanins with surfaces (clay, tissue, gastrointestinal mucosa, etc.) that have many hydroxyl groups. Therefore, the question of determining the approximate pH range is relevant, in which such an interaction is most likely.

The aim of the work was to determine the priority form of the dye (according to the pH of the medium), which can be better fixed on the surface of kaolin.

Simulation of the interaction of cyanidin with the surface of white clay was performed by the Hartree-Fock-Rutaan method, using the GAMESS software package.

The paper presents the results of modeling the interaction of different forms of the anthocyanin model – cyanidin (the content of cyanidin in plants is 50 % of the mass of all types of anthocyanins) in solutions with $\text{pH} < 3$ (red – forms of cyanidin), $3 < \text{pH} < 7$ (violet) and $\text{pH} > 7$ (blue) with a hydroxylated surface of white clay – kaolin, having different types of hydroxyl groups.

The aglycone part of the cyanidin molecule artificially was approached at a distance of approximately 2.5 Å to the surface of kaolin.

It was shown, that the quinoid form of cyanidin (violet) was the most active of the three forms, mainly in interaction with the silanol groups of the kaolin surface. The form of cyanidin at $\text{pH} < 3$ (red) have the lowest energies of interaction with the surface of kaolin.

Keywords: anthocyanin, cyanidin, kaolin, energies of interaction, quantum-chemical calculations.

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1. Introduction

Natural materials for nutrition and cosmetics have many uses and few undesirable effects, which is why there has been growing interest in them in recent years.

In berries, vegetables and fruits with a sweet and sour or astringent taste, their red, purple (violet) and blue colors are mainly due to the presence of anthocyanin pigments in the juice.

The color of anthocyanins changes depending on the pH of the solution, temperature, and light level.

Natural pigments, unlike synthetic ones, are less resistant to external environmental factors. Therefore, it is of interest to search for conditions for obtaining reliable products with anthocyanins [1–11].

To save resources, it is beneficial to use anthocyanins from the waste products of juice and oil production. For example, sustainable natural dyes for textiles were obtained from red chicory waste [2]. From the pomace of blackcurrant berries, hair dyes in shades of blue are found [3].

Since the solution of the pomace extract had a purple color, it was assumed, that reactions of the dye components with the participation of anthocyanins occurred on hair.

It is assumed [4, 5], that during the interaction of clay minerals (and kaolin) with solutions of anthocyanins at different pH, an electrostatic bond is formed between the ingredients.

The surface of kaolin is an excellent model of a hydroxylated surface with the properties of two oxides. That is, with different types of active surface centers.

Anthocyanins, in addition to coloring properties, have a number of health benefits when eaten. Therefore, anthocyanins are promising products for pharmaceuticals.

Anthocyanins can be used in the fight against cardiovascular diseases (CVD), tumors, diabetes, obesity, products with anthocyanins have anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects [6].

In the study of metabolism and elimination of products rich in anthocyanins, it was found [7], that anthocyanins are more bioavailable than previously thought, the maximum metabolism in humans occurs in 6–14 hours, outside the stomach and mainly within and outside the gastrointestinal tract.

In [8], the effect of the type of additive, containing anthocyanins, on the intensity of lipid peroxidation in semi-smoked sausages was studied. It has been shown, that when chokeberry and blackcurrant juice extracts are added to the product, the chokeberry extract helps to slow down the oxidative processes most effectively. It can be assumed, that the advantage of chokeberry extract is related to the pH of the additive solution.

The property of anthocyanins to change color with a change in pH was also supposed to be used in the creation of phytosensors [9, 10].

A brief review of the literature shows that the connection of anthocyanins with the surface of materials and the impact on the processes, occurring in anthocyanin systems – surface (agricultural products, gastrointestinal tract, minerals, textiles, etc.), requires in-depth study both practically and theoretically.

The purpose of the work is to find a model system (models) with the highest values of the energy of interaction between the components, this may also indicate the most favorable conditions for such interaction, in particular – the pH of the medium (solution).

2. Materials

Despite the variety of forms of anthocyanins, all molecules have common properties [10].

Anthocyanin molecules consist of two parts – an aglycone and a carbohydrate part. The aglycone moiety changes as the pH changes. And the carbohydrate part remains unchanged when the pH changes (the composition of this part of the anthocyanin affects the color shade).

The cyanidin molecule is the most convenient for modeling, since the replacement of carbohydrates with hydrogen atoms in the carbohydrate part of a molecule of anthocyanin does not change the properties, but facilitates calculations. In addition, it is known, that in plants cyanidin has the greatest distribution (50 %) [1].

Structural forms of the anthocyanin-cyanidin model: red ($\text{pH} < 3$), violet ($3 < \text{pH} < 7$) and blue ($\text{pH} > 7$) [1–4] are shown in **Table 1**, column 1, 2, 3.

Since when comparing models, it is desirable, that all methods and conditions of calculations were the same, all models had a neutral charge. To do this, the model with a positive charge on the oxygen atom (red) was optimized with a chlorine atom near this oxygen atom, and the anthocyanin model in alkaline medium (blue) with a negative charge near one of the two oxygen atoms (in the ortho position) was optimized with an atom potassium near this atom. The potassium atom in the optimized state of the blue system occupied a central position between these oxygen atoms. The influence of these compensators was taken into account. To minimize the calculation time, a primitive model of kaolinite is constructed, which is shown in **Table 1**, column 4. **Table 1** presents the results of calculations of the total energy of the models.

The arrow indicates the dipole moments in the model molecules (distribution of the sign of the charge from positive to negative).

Despite their small size, the cluster reflects the components of kaolin – the SiO_2 layer and the Al_2O_3 layer [11]. Broken bonds are saturated with hydrogen atoms. At the same time, hydroxyl groups near silicon and aluminum atoms model the hydroxyl coating of the clay surface. Above the aluminum atom in the cluster model of kaolin there is also a molecule of water, which in the FTIR spectra has its own absorption band [4]. The anthocyanin molecule is commensurate with the kaolinite cluster, so there are no steric problems.

Table 1

Structure and total energy (a.u.) of optimized models of kaolinite and anthocyanin in acidic, slightly acidic – neutral and alkaline environments

1	2	3	4
red $E_t = -197.04845$	violet $E_t = -181.7311$	blue $E_t = -181.3937$	kaolin $E_t = -188.6798$

3. Methods

The calculations were performed by the Hartree-Fock method using the SBKJC base set for valence electrons, which uses the effective potential for the backbone electrons using the PC GAMESS software package [12].

4. Results and discussion

Optimized models of dye and clay surfaces artificially approached each other at a distance of about 2.5 Å and optimized this system. The surface of kaolinite can be represented in three main orientations relative to the anthocyanin molecule: the anthocyanin molecule approaches silicon atoms, aluminum atoms (and their hydroxyl groups), and the water molecule above the aluminum atom. It is believed, that the anthocyanin molecule approaches the surface of kaolinite in the part where oxygen atoms are in ortho-positions on the benzene ring, they have strong bonds with protons and cations (in acidic, slightly acidic-neutral and alkaline solutions).

The interaction energies of kaolin with these three forms of anthocyanin are calculated. The main question of the calculations was: in what environment the dye can be better fixed on the surface of the clay? The obtained calculations as well as images of optimized molecular systems “kaolin-cyanidin” are given in **Tables 2–4**.

The greatest energy of the interaction of the kaolin surface with cyanidin in an acidic medium was observed when the flat anthocyanin molecule was oriented by the charged part near the water molecule above the aluminum atom.

The greatest energy of interaction in the system “kaolin surface – cyanidin molecule in the form of violet” was observed when the anthocyanin molecule approached silanol groups, in which the charge on oxygen atoms differs slightly from the charge on the corresponding oxygen atoms near the Al atom (see dipole moment in **Table 1** – of the zone of OH groups of kaolin at Si and Al are close in charge). That is, within such values of the hydrogen index, most reactions occur with the surface, which has hydroxyl groups available for anthocyanin in solution, as well as the decay of the natural dye molecule. In the above publications, the interaction of anthocyanins with a tissue surface, hair, clay, excretion in the gastrointestinal tract occurs mainly in solutions where $\text{pH} > 3$ [1–7]. The effective cessation of lipid oxidation in sausages [8] with chokeberry juice concentrate can also be trivially explained by the fact that chokeberry juice is less acidic than black currant juice.

Table 2

Parameters of model interactions for «red» on the surface of kaolin, pH<3

No.	Model structure, short designation	Total energy, a.u.	Interaction energy, kJ/mol
1	 red+kaolin_Al_OH	-385.7333	13.20
2	 red+kaolin_Si_OH	-385.7406	32.51
3	 red+kaolin_Al_H ₂ O	-385.7555	71.39

Table 3

Parameters of model interactions for «violet» on the surface of kaolin, 3<pH<7

No.	Model structure, short designation	Total energy, a.u.	Interaction energy, kJ / mol
1	 violet+kaolin_Al_OH	-370.43616	66.27
2	 violet+kaolin_Si_OH	-370.47182	159.84
3	 violet+kaolin_Al_H ₂ O	-370.43541	64.31

Table 4

Parameters of model interactions for «blue» on the surface of kaolin, pH > 7

No.	Model structure	Total energy, a.u.	Interaction energy, kJ/mol
1	 blue+kaolin_Al_OH	-370.0973	67.04
2	 blue+kaolin_Si_OH	-370.112	112.30
3	 blue+kaolin_Al_H2O	-370.1203	122.79

For the model system in alkaline solution, the binding energy is greatest when the cyanidin molecule is oriented near the water molecule above the aluminum atom.

A comparison of **Tables 2–4** shows that the quinoid form of cyanidin at $3 < \text{pH} < 7$ has the greatest value of the energy of interaction with the white clay surface (**Table 3**, line 2).

At the same time, acidic solutions ($\text{pH} < 3$) probably contribute to the cleavage of the anthocyanin molecule from the surface, as evidenced by the low values of the interaction energy. In this regard, the well-known old method of removing fresh juices from tissues by immersion in an acid solution is recalled, so that the stain can then be easily washed off. Therefore, natural dyes from red berries are the most unstable.

High values of the interaction energy between the cyanidin molecule and the kaolin surface in the area of the water molecule above the aluminum atom attract attention. These values are lower than the highest values of the interaction energy when cyanidin approaches silanol groups, however, when the active components of the mixture are selected, the interaction reaction with the surface can be accelerated.

5. Conclusions

Thus, it is shown, that the interaction of cyanidin with the hydroxylated surface of kaolin is more effective at $3 < \text{pH} < 7$, cyanidin reacts mainly with silanol groups. High values of the energy of interaction in the model systems in acidic and alkaline media are conditioned by the presence of water molecules in kaolin over the aluminum atom.

The implementation of effective interactions of cyanidin with the surface of kaolin in alkaline media is possible under additional conditions and requires further study.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

References

- [1] Khoo, H. E., Azlan, A., Tang, S. T., Lim, S. M. (2017). Anthocyanidins and anthocyanins: colored pigments as food, pharmaceutical ingredients, and the potential health benefits. *Food & Nutrition Research*, 61 (1), 1361779. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/16546628.2017.1361779>
- [2] Gecchele, E., Negri, S., Cauzzi, A., Cuccurullo, A., Commisso, M., Patrucco, A. et. al. (2021). Optimization of a Sustainable Protocol for the Extraction of Anthocyanins as Textile Dyes from Plant Materials. *Molecules*, 26 (22), 6775. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226775>
- [3] Rose, P. M., Cantrill, V., Benohoud, M., Tidder, A., Rayner, C. M., Blackburn, R. S. (2018). Application of Anthocyanins from Blackcurrant (*Ribes nigrum* L.) Fruit Waste as Renewable Hair Dyes. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 66 (26), 6790–6798. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.8b01044>
- [4] Li, S., Mu, B., Wang, X., Kang, Y., Wang, A. (2019). A Comparative Study on Color Stability of Anthocyanin Hybrid Pigments Derived from 1D and 2D Clay Minerals. *Materials*, 12 (20), 3287. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12203287>
- [5] Hashemian, S., Reza Shahedi, M. (2013). Novel Ag/Kaolin Nanocomposite as Adsorbent for Removal of Acid Cyanine 5R from Aqueous Solution. *Journal of Chemistry*, 2013, 1–7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/285671>
- [6] He, K., Li, X., Chen, X., Ye, X., Huang, J., Jin, Y. et. al. (2011). Evaluation of antidiabetic potential of selected traditional Chinese medicines in STZ-induced diabetic mice. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 137 (3), 1135–1142. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2011.07.033>
- [7] Czank, C., Cassidy, A., Zhang, Q., Morrison, D. J., Preston, T., Kroon, P. A. et. al. (2013). Human metabolism and elimination of the anthocyanin, cyanidin-3-glucoside: a ¹³C-tracer study. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 97 (5), 995–1003. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.112.049247>
- [8] Pasichnyi, V., Bozhko, N., Tischenko, V., Marynin, A., Shubina, Y., Svyatnenko, R. et. al. (2022). Study of efficiency of berry extracts in the technology of semi-smoked sausages. *EUREKA: Life Sciences*, 1, 25–31. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5695.2022.002286>
- [9] Naghdi, T., Faham, S., Mahmoudi, T., Pourreza, N., Ghavami, R., Golmohammadi, H. (2020). Phytochemicals toward Green (Bio)sensing. *ACS Sensors*, 5 (12), 3770–3805. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.0c02101>
- [10] Zhang, X., Lu, S., Chen, X. (2014). A visual pH sensing film using natural dyes from *Bauhinia blakeana* Dunn. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, 198, 268–273. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2014.02.094>
- [11] Karmous, M. S. (2011). Theoretical Study of Kaolinite Structure; Energy Minimization and Crystal Properties. *World Journal of Nano Science and Engineering*, 01 (02), 62–66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4236/wjnse.2011.12009>
- [12] Schmidt, M. W., Baldrige, K. K., Boatz, J. A., Elbert, S. T., Gordon, M. S., Jensen, J. H. et. al. (1993). General atomic and molecular electronic structure system. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 14 (11), 1347–1363. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.540141112>

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